

Investigating Communication Between Certified Nursing Assistants and Senior Residents In Boca Raton Assisted Living Facilities

Abstract

While Certified Nursing Assistants (CNAs) provide the vast majority of care in long-term care settings, their communication adequacy remains underresearched. This mixed-methods study quantified the perceptual communication gap between CNAs and senior residents across 12 Assisted Living Facilities (ALFs) in Boca Raton, Florida. Quantitative t-tests revealed statistically significant discrepancies ($p < 0.0001$) across seven evaluated aspects of the CNA-resident relationship, with the most notable effect sizes being on the teach-back method ($d = 1.73$) and resident involvement ($d = 1.48$). Further qualitative coding identified 'Repetition without Adaptation' and 'Efficiency over Empathy' as the primary barriers to this disconnect. Although the baseline communication gap did not statistically correlate with lower medication adherence scores ($r = -0.133$), the data exposes a trust-understanding gap where residents trust their caregivers but remain mentally isolated from their treatment plans, emphasizing the need for personalized communication strategies in CNA training.

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Introduction

In long-term care settings, Certified Nursing Assistants (CNAs) account for the vast majority of senior resident care (Pennington et al., 2003). Yet, despite this, their role as communicators is often overlooked. This reflects a broader gap in the current literature, as most existing research has been done in short-term care, rather than long-term care. Specifically leveraging the many Assisted Living Facilities (ALFs) in Boca Raton, this study aimed to address the lack of research quantifying the perceptual discrepancy between CNA self-reported communication adequacy and resident comprehension. Through a dual survey, which had one path designed for CNAs and the other for senior residents, it was found that there is a statistically significant discrepancy in perceptions, which could be negatively correlated to treatment adherence, as hypothesized. Therefore, this study provides a new understanding of how CNAs tend to overestimate their communication skills compared to senior residents' understanding based on quantitative and qualitative results. Most notably, the negative correlation rank produced by Spearman's rank correlation ($r_s = -0.133$) and four themes coded for suggest that low health literacy and medication non-adherence among senior resident participants were a result of miscommunication, which could improve community health if addressed.

Literature Review

Section I. Health Literacy and the Consequences of Non-Adherence

Treatment adherence can be defined as the “prevention of complications and successful control” of disease, which relies on patients’ active participation in treatment (Maghsoudi et al., 2023). When patients do not adhere to the preventative regimens instated by healthcare providers, “treatment failure, increased complications of disease, longer treatment duration, increased healthcare costs and increased patient mortality” often ensue (Maghsoudi et al., 2023).

Complex medication regimens to treat multiple diseases are becoming increasingly common “with the aging of the U.S. population...Nevertheless, patients often do not fully understand the instructions for safe and effective medication use” (Marvanova et al., 2011). Given that older people are particularly susceptible to various diseases and disabilities, researchers Maghsoudi et al. point out—similarly to Marvanova et al.—that aging has become “one of the most important health challenges worldwide” (2023). Maghsoudi’s team conducted a study on older people, specifically with Type 2 Diabetes, and concluded that adherence depends on a patient’s health literacy, treatment responsibility, and support umbrella. In their study, patients who had “effective interactions” with their caretaker felt involved and motivated to follow medication plans (2023). Thus, negative health outcomes from non-adherence can be avoided by improving health literacy and strengthening nurse-patient communication. This notion is supported by Coskun and Bagcivan, whose study proves that “patients’ adherence to treatment increased as their health literacy increased” through a statistically significant positive correlation ($r_s = 0.604$) between the Adult Health Literacy Scale and Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (2021). By proving a correlation, Coskun and Bagcivan establish the high-stakes outcome of the current public health crisis caused by poor understanding of medical information, especially among seniors with chronic illnesses (2021).

The city of Boca Raton, Florida, has a vast senior community as a result of its many nursing homes, rehabilitation centers, and assisted living facilities (ALFs); Apple Maps searches show 15 ALFs in the area alone. This explains why a majority of the population of Boca Raton is aged 65-66, according to Statistical Atlas, whose data is based on authoritative sources like the U.S. Census Bureau’s American Community Survey (2018). For this research paper, the focus will be on the many chronically ill seniors within Boca Raton, since there is a need to assess how

the modern healthcare system affects their health literacy, treatment adherence, and relationship to caregivers. Considering the unique barriers to adherence faced by older people, newer research to assess this demographic today has the potential to impact community health in a town densely populated by seniors.

Section II. Recent Research on Nurse-Patient Relationships

As far back as the 1960s, the importance of nurses' attitudes toward informing patients has been recognized and in-depthly studied. Namely, Dodge designed his 1961 study to measure nurses' attitudes toward themselves, their patients, and patient care, guiding the method for the nursing side of this research paper by demonstrating how nurses perceive the effectiveness of their communication. Despite this relationship between nurses and patients being studied for decades, it remains continually underresearched in relation to treatment adherence. Recent studies evaluating the relationship in modern contexts acknowledge the fact that "research is still lacking on the association between satisfaction with physician-patient communication and adherence to treatment or self-care in chronically ill patients" (Świątoniowska-Lonc et al., 2020). This confirms the historical and continuous need for research on the nurse perspective—in addition to that of chronically ill senior patients—factoring in communication and treatment adherence.

Since the target group of seniors has been established, the type of nurses included as the second target group is contingent on where many seniors with chronic illnesses reside: long-term care settings. Caregivers such as CNAs in these settings are often underrepresented in the nurse-patient relationship, making them an important group to study.

It is known that general doctors and patients "do not always gain mutual understanding, and their expectations, perspectives may be completely different" (Świątoniowska-Lonc et al.,

2020). Nurses in particular are seen to be deficient in communication when discussing the next steps in patients' treatment plans and involving them in decision-making (Świątoniowska-Lonc et al., 2020). Aliafsari et al., who examined 302 cardiovascular patients, stress the importance of trust in nurse-patient relationships as it is directly linked to treatment adherence (2024). The American Nurses Association corroborates that nurses should directly involve patients in treatment and decision-making to build trust, ultimately leading to "better health outcomes and increase[d] patient satisfaction" (2023). The study by Świątoniowska-Lonc et al. hence serves as an example of miscommunication when healthcare providers do not adhere to modern standards for fostering trust: patients who reported that their physician did not encourage them to ask questions (28.4%), involve them in decisions (29.2%), or discuss the next steps (35.2%) "had a low level of adherence to pharmaceutical treatment" (2020).

However, whether this disconnect found in doctors and nurses translates directly to CNAs with residents is unknown; if it does, then the question becomes about how their differing perspectives impact treatment adherence. Evaluating the two perspectives would allow for an accurate judgment of the modern nurse-patient relationship in long-term care settings by comparing seniors' perceptions of communication with their CNAs and further linking it to medication adherence.

Section III. Healthcare Setting Shortcomings and the Importance of CNAs

Much of the existing literature centers around short-term care, primarily within hospitals, leading to a lack of research in long-term, end-of-life care settings (Aliafsari et al., 2024; Coskun & Bagcivan, 2021; Dodge, 1961; Marvanova et al., 2011; Rashidi et al., 2025). Reflecting on Section I., Marvanova et al.'s research was conducted in two hospitals, meaning that their association between "lower health literacy" and "less understanding of the pre-admission

medication regimen” may not mirror challenges in long-term care settings. Similarly, the link between trust in the nurse-patient relationship and treatment adherence found by Aliafsari et al. may not translate to long-term care settings, as it was within the domain of a hospital. For this reason, Hyvert et al. emphasize that future research should investigate communication strategies tailored to the specific environment of long-term chronic care (2023). As a result, part of the gap explored covers local ALFs and chronic care rather than acute care.

Another part of the gap, as mentioned in Section II., is the exclusion of CNAs due to underrepresentation in the nurse-patient relationship and the shortfall of research in long-term care settings. Such exclusion is evidenced by Biola et al., whose study on communication in end-of-life facilities focuses on physicians and family caregivers, yet fails to account for the dominant communication roles held by CNAs (2007). In fact, CNAs “provide 80% to 90% of the care to residents,” which is “two times greater than [Registered Nurses] and [Licensed Practical Nurses] combined” (Pennington et al., 2003). Despite their importance in communication and care, the current pool of CNAs is “dwindling,” making it more critical than ever to understand their experiences for enhanced senior care today (Pennington et al. 2003). Zheng and Temkin-Greener concur that CNA communication should be better understood, especially because “no empirical studies have focused specifically on the impact of CNA[s]” (2010). Their results from 2363 New York CNAs are “not...generalizable to other states,” providing a foundation for development in Boca Raton (2010).

Section IV. The Overall Gap

In view of the dense senior population of Boca Raton and the current health literacy challenges they face, a missing link remains between treatment adherence and nurse-patient communication in long-term care. Karttunen et al. provide one of the few studies on long-term

care, but their target remains solely on caregivers through self-assessment techniques (2020). While notable, this research points to a major methodological gap by failing to compare nurses' self-reported adequacy to residents' comprehension of medical instruction. Therefore, the extent to which residents understood the care or treatment plans explained by nurses cannot be validated. Given that no modern studies have examined the discrepancy between nurse- and patient-perceived communication adequacy, this paper will assess both perspectives. By comparing these results, it will avoid one-sided data and reach valid conclusions regarding the impact of communication on treatment adherence.

To equally cover the setting and population gaps, this research will be carried out in ALFs, a prevalent long-term care setting in Boca Raton. As explored in Section I., Boca Raton is ideal for covering these gaps because of its large senior community, which ensures maximized participants, and therefore, a more generalizable conclusion. Furthermore, the setting of ALFs allows the theme of nurse-patient communication—which, as established in Section II., has been extensively studied—to be narrowed down to CNA-resident communication. Internal medicine researchers Lindquist et al. explain that learning about CNAs' health literacy and perceptions could provide residents with “optimal care” (2011). Accordingly, the method of this paper will include both CNA self-assessment and the first-hand opinion of residents directly affected by their communication, accomplished through a dual survey.

It is hypothesized that there will be a difference in their perceptions of medical instruction comprehensibility because communication issues are a two-way deficit, reinforcing the need to survey both sides. The results could then be connected to residents' treatment adherence to investigate whether a difference in perspectives is negatively correlated with their medication adherence. Understanding this correlation may help elucidate why seniors with

chronic illnesses struggle most with treatment adherence, therefore contributing to the improvement of community health since adherence is “linked to mortality, morbidity, and quality of life” (Rashidi et al., 2025). Such new research would additionally help gain insight into how current healthcare practices shape medical relationships and the impact they have on modern-day seniors.

Method

This study aimed to explore the discrepancy between CNA self-reported communication adequacy and the consequent understanding of senior residents. To directly compare their differing perspectives, a correlational-descriptive, cross-sectional design was implemented through a dual survey. In this study, dual surveying refers to a survey in which two paths can be taken, depending on whether the respondent is a CNA or a resident; those who did not give consent or did not fit into either group were directed to the submit page and excluded from the study (see Appendix B.). Although questions for both sides mirrored each other, they were phrased in a way intended for either CNAs or residents. This parallel questioning ensured that the same communication behaviors were being measured for each target group, allowing for objective comparison, necessary to justify the hypothesized difference in perceptions. Ultimately, the purpose of this study was to explore how such perceptual differences, if found, may have impacted treatment adherence among senior residents with chronic illnesses in Boca Raton ALFs.

As aforementioned in the Literature Review, the setting of Boca Raton was chosen due to the large senior demographic and its many ALFs. For a comprehensive analysis, all 15 ALFs shown within Boca Raton on Apple Maps were contacted, covering a public rating spectrum of 1.8 to 5.0 stars. The dual survey was administered digitally through Google Forms for

maximized efficiency, as the path separation feature allowed for automatic distinction between the two target groups: CNAs regularly providing medical care and senior residents who manage chronic medication regimens (see Appendix B.). It is important to note that CNAs do not often directly give medical instruction, but in long-term care settings, they can be trained and authorized to administer medication or assist with self-administration (*DeSantis Signs Measure*, 2023). This makes CNAs influential to residents' treatment adherence and a potential correlational factor that needs to be studied.

Initially, the sampling strategy had been to email, call, voicemail, and text the selected ALFs, then carry out the study in those who were able to administer the survey in compliance with the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act. After two weeks of waiting, this passive form of data collection had not produced any results, which caused a change to active data collection. Colorful flyers with QR codes linked to the survey (see Appendix A.) were distributed to all 15 ALFs in person with the goal of getting CNAs and senior residents to conveniently scan and respond. When only CNAs were responding, it became evident that the digital survey was too technologically complicated for seniors in end-of-life care. With the permission of the Directors of Nursing, senior residents were interviewed one by one with the structured survey questions until 30 responses were reached, all organized through Google Sheets. Reaching 30 responses per target group was necessary not only to ensure equal sample representation for later side-by-side analysis, but also to satisfy the Central Limit Theorem. This theorem states that as sample sizes get larger ($n \geq 30$), the distribution of sample means approaches normality regardless of the population's original shape (*Central Limit Theorem*, n.d.). Hence, normal-distribution-based statistics—like the *t*-tests that will be involved in this study—can be calculated even when data is not normally distributed.

For objective statistical testing, eight of the ten items included in each path were closed, quantitative questions. These questions rendered data analysis easier and the overall survey format simpler for busy CNAs as well as fatigable elderly residents. The first three were Likert scales, from 1 to 5, giving respondents a range of numerical options between “Not very clear/Not often at all/Not very trustworthy” (1) and “Extremely clear/Very often/Extremely trustworthy” (5). Such a range elicited self-assessment, thus providing a valid measure for the communication clarity of CNAs, their use of simplified medical terms, and trustworthiness. The subsequent four multiple-choice questions required participants to place themselves in the situation presented by phrasing the question as a personal statement with “I” for CNAs and “My” for residents. After reflecting on personal experience in long-term care, they could respond with “Strongly disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree, or Strongly agree.” Likert scale and multiple-choice questions were mainly inspired by the communication guidelines of geriatric medicine researchers Peng et al., which explain how healthcare providers must use strategies like the teach-back method and simple language when communicating with older adults (2015). The last of the eight closed, quantitative questions was a checkbox selection where respondents could “Check all that apply” from a list of four qualities—attentiveness, patience, open-mindedness, and inquisitiveness—derived from the American Nurses Association article detailed in Section II. of the Literature Review. According to the 2023 article, these four active listening qualities nurture trust in the nurse-patient relationship, making it crucial to understand which ones CNAs exhibit and at what frequencies. Two open-ended questions were additionally included for the total of ten questions to gain a personal view into participants' perceptions of communication behaviors. Communication can be an emotional topic, meriting a deeper dive into individual, self-reported experiences that closed questions could not have covered. As a result, the final two short-answer

questions were designed to create space for CNAs and residents to use their own words to explain how they typically try to communicate medical information.

Focusing on the CNA section, the ten questions were given to assess their communication behaviours and concluded their path (see Appendix C.). However, senior residents were first led to a section containing seven items on health literacy and treatment adherence before proceeding to the section with their corresponding ten questions (see Appendices D. and E.). These seven items combined two widely validated questionnaires, both chosen for their short duration to prevent demotivating patients: the 3-item Brief Health Literacy Screener (BHLS) and the 4-item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-4) (Wallston et al., 2014; Rosen et al., 2017; Coskun & Bagcivan, 2021). Health literacy levels—measured through BHLS scores—were analyzed as a potential extraneous variable to ensure that findings isolated communication adequacy rather than general health knowledge.

Given the two types of data collected (quantitative and qualitative), results were planned to be analyzed through a mixed-methods approach, all showcased in a radar chart, scatter plot, and thematic chart. Quantitative analysis first involved independent two-sample *t*-tests to identify statistically significant gaps between CNA self-assessment and resident perceptions across the Likert scale and multiple-choice questions. If the probability value (*p*-value) is less than the established significance level of 0.05, it can be concluded that the difference is statistically significant, therefore validating that the communication gap is not due to chance (American Psychological Association, 2020). However, determining the exact size of the gap was done by another test called Cohen's *d*; the effect sizes found through the *d*-value can be categorized as small (0.2), medium (0.5), or large (0.8) (McLeod, 2023). Spearman's rank correlation was then used to quantify the relationship between baseline discrepancy (mean CNA score - individual

resident score) and medication adherence (individual MMAS-4 scores); the closer the r_s value is to -1 or 1, the stronger the correlation. The final numerical measure was the checkbox question, which was analyzed in simple percentages for each of the four choices. To provide depth to the numerical findings, the two open-ended responses underwent thematic coding, categorizing specific barriers to comprehension.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were essential in this research process due to the sensitive nature of senior residents receiving end-of-life care. For this reason, the first question on the dual survey, before moving on to either the CNA or senior resident section, was “Do you have the mental capacity and time to take this survey?” (see Appendix B.). Limiting respondents to patients with the cognitive ability to consent meant that unfit participants could click “No” and submit the survey to opt out. Nevertheless, a validated scale was incorporated into the senior side of the survey, meaning that all 7 BHLS and MMAS-4 questions had to be required. Since this was necessary to maintain the reliability of the data, a bolded disclaimer at the top of the survey clarified that participants who felt uncomfortable could exit the survey entirely at any time, which would automatically discard their progress (see Appendix B.). Informed consent was equally emphasized in bold, explaining why the research is being conducted, the right to withdraw, and how responses would be kept confidential. The anonymity of respondents maintained participant confidentiality by ensuring no tracking data, facility names, or personal identities were collected, simultaneously limiting social desirability bias as well.

Results

Over the course of one month, active data collection yielded 60 total responses, evenly split between 30 CNAs and 30 senior residents. Given this sample size, the Central Limit Theorem applies, indicating a normal distribution for mean statistics. Respondents were drawn from 12 of the 15 ALFs in Boca Raton, therefore covering 80% of ALFs in the area. All survey questions were answered, except for three CNA responses on the first open question, four on the second, and three missed checkbox responses from residents.

Examining the health literacy of senior residents, 23.3% of those surveyed had ‘Adequate’ health literacy, averaging 6.53 out of 12 on the BHLS. Similarly, medication adherence was relatively low among residents surveyed, with the average MMAS-4 score being 2.63 out of 4. Consequently, health literacy and medication adherence must be factored into the reasoning for any communication discrepancies.

To identify these discrepancies, *t*-tests were run for each pair of parallel questions using responses ordinally encoded from 1 to 5. For instance, Question 1 responses from the CNA section were tested against those from the senior resident section to directly compare perspectives on communication clarity (see Appendices C. and E.). This continued up until Question 7, which was the last of the Likert scale and multiple-choice questions. Cohen’s *d* was then calculated to determine the exact effect size and magnitude of the disconnect between CNAs and senior residents. Both the *t*-test calculations and Cohen’s *d* for Questions 1 through 7 are organized in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1. Quantitative Discrepancy Chart

Question	Description	CNA Mean	Resident Mean	Gap Score	<i>p</i> -value (t-test)	Cohen's <i>d</i>	Effect Size / Magnitude
1	Clarity	4.57	3.67	0.90	0.0007	0.93	Large Effect
2	Simplified Language	4.60	3.93	0.67	0.0122	0.67	Medium Effect
3	Trustworthy	4.70	4.03	0.67	0.0042	0.77	Medium-Large Effect
4	Teach Back	4.47	2.50	1.97	< 0.0001	1.73	Large Effect / Critical Disconnect
5	New Medication	4.37	3.40	0.97	0.0005	0.95	Large Effect (mainly Neutral)
6	Involve in Care	4.63	3.00	1.63	< 0.0001	1.48	Large Effect / High Disconnect
7	Confident in Plan	4.60	3.43	1.17	0.00003	1.20	Large Effect / High Disconnect

As clarified in the Literature Review, a *p*-value lower than 0.05 is statistically significant, revealing a significant gap between CNA and resident communication perspectives across all seven questions. Correspondingly, all seven questions produced medium to large effect sizes since the *d*-values exceeded the benchmarks of 0.5 and 0.8, respectively. It is important to note that the wide majority of respondents answered 'Neutral' to Question 5—"I explain the purpose, dosage, and possible side effects of any new medication"—because CNAs do not handle new medications as often as licensed nursing staff do. Therefore, the results produced for Question 5 are presented to maintain the structural continuity of the survey, but should be interpreted with caution, prompting their exclusion from the Discussion.

Figure 2. Radar Chart of CNA-Resident Discrepancy

The above radar chart supports the statistical analysis summarized in *Figure 1* by showcasing the physical gap in perceptions. Moreover, the blue ring representing CNAs completely engulfs the red ring representing senior residents, expanding farther out to ‘5.’ This ‘5’ corresponds to the highest value on the Likert scale and multiple-choice questions, implying that CNAs rate their care higher than residents.

With the gap between CNA self-reported communication adequacy and senior resident understanding being established, Spearman’s rank correlation was run between baseline discrepancy and individual medication adherence scores. A loose negative correlation was found between the two variables ($r_s = -0.133$), as shown in the scatter plot below, where the red line depicts the negative correlation coefficient.

Figure 3. Correlational Scatter Plot

Despite a correlation rank of -0.133, it did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.4824$).

This means that there is a 48% chance the r_s -value produced was due to coincidence, far exceeding the benchmark for statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). Dots on the scatter plot are spread out, which visually explains why the p -value is not significant.

Figure 4. CNA Checkbox Question Bar Graph

Figure 5. Resident Checkbox Question Bar Graph

The last of the closed questions was the checkbox selection, which could not be ordinarily encoded from 1 to 5. For this reason, a side-by-side bar graph was created to compare perceptions on the attentiveness, patience, open-mindedness, and inquisitiveness of CNAs. Only for this question were the results similar, as both target groups found CNAs to be patient and attentive, but to a lesser degree inquisitive. Among CNA respondents, 93.3% of them chose ‘Patience,’ while 63% of resident respondents chose ‘Patience’ and ‘Attentiveness.’ Thus, CNAs generally follow the American Nurses Association guidelines for fostering trust (2023).

Figure 6. Thematically Coded Open Question Responses (Resident Focus)

Theme	Open Codes / Keywords	Resident Frequency	Representative Quotes
Repetition without Adaptation	“Repeat” “Over and over” “Say it again” “No other way”	21 / 30 (70%)	Resident: “They keep repeating information until I get it, but they don't do much else.”
			CNA: “I start out by talking slowly... repeating as the resident needs.”
Efficiency over Empathy	“Move on” “Straight to point” “Pill count” “Rushed”	12 / 30 (40%)	Resident: “I know how many pills I have to take, but I couldn't tell you what they're for.” Resident: “They explain, get straight to the point, and move on.”
Illusion of Autonomy	“Her way” “Do not listen/care” “Walker” “No choice”	9 / 30 (30%)	Resident: “She said it's either her way or my way, and obviously, she chose her way.” Resident: “None of the examples apply because they do not listen and they do not care.”
Digital & Relational Barriers	“Earphones/Phone” “Neighbor” “Avoid” “Busy”	7 / 30 (23%)	Resident: “This one CNA is always wearing those earphones...they won't pay attention.” Resident: “They will avoid coming to me because I'm always asking for help.”

Through thematic coding of open-ended responses, four main themes emerged that added contextual depth to the quantitative findings. The most frequent theme of ‘Repetition without Adaptation’ was identified in 21 out of 30 resident responses. While most CNAs cited repetition as an effective method of communication, 70% of residents felt that this repetition prevented CNAs from adapting medical instruction to their level of understanding. Furthermore, the ‘Efficiency over Empathy’ theme was found in 40% of resident responses, with 12 residents describing a focus on medication tasks rather than education of their treatment plans. This was further supported by the ‘Illusion of Autonomy’ theme, where 30% of residents reported feeling that care was led entirely by CNAs rather than being collaborative. A smaller portion of the sample (23%) additionally identified ‘Digital and Relational Barriers,’ mentioning the use of cellular devices or earphones by staff during medical interactions.

Discussion

While most nurse-patient relationship research focuses on short-term care settings, this study investigates the specific interactions between CNAs and the residents they take care of in the long-term care ALFs of Boca Raton. Expanding upon the methodology of Karttunen et al., this research moves beyond one-sided assessment by implementing a dual survey approach that compares both CNA and resident perspectives (2020). Synthesizing statistical results with resident narratives reveals a profound communication gap. This gap is negatively correlated with treatment adherence, suggesting that as the perceptual disconnect widens, resident adherence tends to decrease. Although this correlation did not reach statistical significance, it aligns with the initial hypothesis that a discrepancy in perceptions hinders adherence. Factors such as unexpectedly low health literacy levels and other variables that could not be accounted for within the brief survey may have contributed to the statistical insignificance, unlike hypothesized. This mirrors the “inconsistent” link found by Hyvert et al. between literacy and adherence (2023). Overall, the quantitative and qualitative findings of this study support the idea that residents’ low health literacy and poor adherence stem from the false confidence of CNAs, who believe their communication is effective despite resident confusion.

Analyzing the quantitative results, it is crucial to highlight that the widest perceptual differences were on the teach-back method ($p < 0.0001$, $d = 1.73$) and active involvement of residents in care ($p < 0.0001$, $d = 1.48$). Contrastingly, CNAs and residents found the questions on simplified language ($p = 0.0122$, $d = 0.67$) and trustworthiness ($p = 0.0042$, $d = 0.77$) somewhat agreeable, producing the only medium effect sizes out of all seven questions. These discrepancies are attributable to CNAs overrating their communication adequacy, as illustrated by the engulfing blue ring in the radar chart (*Figure 2*). The deepest valleys in the radar chart

correspond to the questions on the teach-back method and involvement in care, matching results from the *t*-tests and Cohen's *d*. Alongside the peak for trustworthiness, these valleys point to a dangerous trust-understanding gap. Considering that 63% of residents found CNAs to be patient and attentive as well (*Figures 4 and 5*), residents in this study were satisfied with their CNAs, but still struggled to understand their medical instructions. This contradicts the findings of Świątoniowska-Lonc et al., who argued that patient satisfaction usually leads to adherence. As the correlation rank of -0.133 suggests, the trust-understanding gap leads to lower adherence, with residents averaging only 2.63 out of 4 on the MMAS-4.

Examining the qualitative results, four main themes emerged from resident responses (*Figure 6*), all indicating that the Boca Raton ALFs fail to follow the "Universal Precautions" recommended by Peng et al. (2015). Interpreting these themes, 'Efficiency over Empathy' may have risen from the limited time CNAs have to take care of all their patients, which does not allow for personalized care. These time constraints force a reliance on strict routines, explaining why 'Repetition without Adaptation' prevents CNAs from personalizing care to individual cognitive levels. When compared to resident responses, CNAs largely overrated their communication adequacy, as their perceived teaching was considered a task by residents. As a result, many residents could not understand their treatment plans, explaining why they felt excluded from decision-making and the ongoing treatment process. This disconnect corresponds to the significant discrepancies found in *Figure 1* and the visible valleys of the radar chart in *Figure 2*; specifically, the 'Repetition without Adaptation' theme accounts for the failure of the teach-back method, while the 'Illusion of Autonomy' theme provides the context for why residents felt excluded from their own care.

Revisiting Section II. of the Literature Review, the findings propose that the disconnect found between doctors and nurses with their patients does translate over to the CNA-resident relationship (Świątoniowska-Lonc et al., 2020; Aliafsari et al., 2024; American Nurses Association, 2023). Therefore, initial thinking that the disconnect would translate over and be correlated to lower treatment adherence was justified, solidifying the need for Spearman's rank correlation. All of the *t*-tests and Cohen's *d* statistics, as well as the MMAS-4 and BHLS measures, led up to the final correlation rank ($r_s = -0.133$) that could be contextualized through thematic coding. Having established a loose trend between baseline discrepancy and individual MMAS-4 scores, the trust-understanding gap and false confidence create the new understanding that residents trust their CNAs, but do not understand their medical instruction. Reinforced by the 'Repetition without Adaptation' theme, CNAs paradoxically believed they were communicating effectively through repetition, while residents experienced low understanding in reality.

Since the correlation yielded a p-value of 0.4824, far beyond the threshold of $p < 0.05$, this statistical insignificance suggests that medication adherence in Boca Raton ALFs is maintained by CNAs handling medication rather than resident understanding. In other words, patients may be physically compliant, yet they are mentally isolated from their own care. Such isolation directly exposes the 'Illusion of Autonomy' theme, further implying that adequate adherence scores do not reflect health literacy. Consequently, if seniors were hypothetically removed from this rigid institutional safety net, their capacity for independent medicine self-management would remain dangerously low.

This new understanding validates the "shared responsibility" model detailed by Lindquist et al., which defines health literacy as a combination of patient skill and caregiver

communication (2011). Since caregiver communication was rated poorly by residents, and knowing that CNAs exhibited a false confidence in their care, the average BHLS score of 6.53 out of 12 is coherent. Hence, communication can be described as the foundation of adherence, similar to how Maghsoudi et al. consider communication to be the center of care (2023).

Accounting for the importance of communication, the results of this study could have massive implications for community health in Boca Raton ALFs. If left unaddressed, the discrepancy in perceptions between CNAs and senior residents could lead to a gradual worsening of resident adherence to their treatment plans. It is imperative that we ensure all residents feel included in the treatment process to avoid the negative consequences of non-adherence, which are associated with mortality (Rashidi et al., 2025).

Conclusion

This study investigated the discrepancy between CNA self-reported communication clarity and senior resident understanding, and how it impacts treatment adherence. The findings suggest that there is a significant discrepancy in the CNA-resident relationship, as well as a less notable negative correlation between miscommunication and low treatment adherence. These results indicate that CNAs and senior residents often do not gain a mutual understanding, which is likely one of the main factors causing low treatment adherence among those surveyed. The implications of this study apply to both CNAs and residents, as it provides the data necessary to demonstrate failed communication and, therefore, teach CNAs that their heightened bias towards their own quality of care does not reflect actual resident understanding. A potential solution is for CNAs to learn to break away from strict guidelines and personalize care instead—as the thematic coding suggests—helping residents better understand and better adhere to treatment. If these patterns hold true in a broader context, widespread non-adherence could be ameliorated by

strengthening overall CNA-resident communication. Given that low treatment adherence has dangerous consequences (explored in Literature Review), CNAs not only in the senior community of Boca Raton, but across the world should be taught during training to adapt their instructions to individual needs. Otherwise, senior residents in underresearched long-term care facilities will continue to remain silently affected by preventable negative health outcomes.

Limitations/Need for Further Research

Considering that CNAs vastly overrated their care compared to senior residents, social desirability bias may have led them to choose the socially desirable answer over the truth (Villar, 2008). Since it is ultimately up to each participant to choose the truth, there are no real solutions to social desirability bias, although ensuring that responses will be anonymous partially relieves pressure to answer in a way that is socially acceptable. Residents could have equally been pressured to answer with more socially desirable responses since I interviewed them directly instead of having them scan a QR code like CNAs. In the dual survey, anonymity was clarified in bold in the short disclaimer at the top to prevent this bias from occurring in both target groups (see Appendix B.).

All participants came strictly from Assisted Living Facilities in Boca Raton, meaning that results can only be generalized to that geographical area. Despite meeting the minimum requirement for the Central Limit Theorem, the number of responses corresponds to a Type II error (small sample size). Alternatively, it suggests that while communication fails, Boca Raton residents may still adhere to medication due to other factors not included in this study. This is logical when looking at the statistical insignificance of the correlation rank. Thus, future research should evaluate different factors in the multifaceted CNA-resident relationship with a sample size of $N > 100$ and participants from different communities. While Boca Raton was selected to

maximize responses, exploring different communities with varying senior density is necessary to ensure the findings apply to a broader context.

As for the health literacy and medication adherence factors accounted for, the BHLS and MMAS-4 are limited in what they measure. Moreover, the BHLS measures health literacy in only two domains: access to information and understanding information (Dijkman et al., 2024). Likewise, the MMAS-4 only contains 4 items to assess adherence, collecting surface-level data. Although both measures have been proven to “[demonstrate] adequate reliability and validity,” future studies should include more in-depth screeners for health literacy and medication adherence to account for the complex nature of treatment (Wallston et al., 2014; Coskun & Bagcivan, 2021; Rosen et al., 2017).

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Appendix A. Distributed QR Code Flyer

TIME TO SURVEY

**CALLING ALL CERTIFIED
NURSING ASSISTANTS
AND SENIOR RESIDENTS**

Please help a student researcher complete their paper by scanning the QR code and taking a brief survey. Thank you so much!

Appendix B. Exclusion Criteria Opening Questions

Evaluating the CNA-Resident Relationship and Perceptions of Medical Instruction Clarity

The following survey is for educational purposes only. This instrument is administered solely to facilitate an independent research study focused on personal academic development and an advanced understanding of long-term care systems. All individual responses will be **anonymous** and kept **confidential**. You may choose to **opt out** of the survey for any reason at any time. You **do not** have to answer any questions that you do not feel comfortable answering, unless they are required. If a **required** question makes you feel uncomfortable, you can **exit** the survey entirely.

████████████████████ [Switch account](#)

Not shared

Do you understand the terms stated above and have the mental capacity to take this survey?

Yes

No

[Next](#)

[Clear form](#)

If 'No' is chosen:

Click submit to finish

[Back](#)

[Submit](#)

[Clear form](#)

This survey is designed for Certified Nursing Assistants and senior residents only. If you are neither, you will be taken to the submit page directly.

Are you a Certified Nursing Assistant or senior resident?

- Certified Nursing Assistant (CNA)
- Senior Resident
- Neither

[Back](#)

[Next](#)

[Clear form](#)

If 'Neither' is chosen:

Click submit to finish

[Back](#)

[Submit](#)

[Clear form](#)

Appendix C. Certified Nursing Assistant Section

Certified Nursing Assistants

Please answer the following questions about communication using your personal experience and knowledge of caretaking in long-term care settings.

On a scale of 1 to 5, how clear would you say your communication to residents is in regards to medication adherence and treatment plans?

1 2 3 4 5

Not very clear Extremely clear

On a scale of 1 to 5, how often do you believe you use simplified medical language when giving instructions to residents?

1 2 3 4 5

Not often at all Extremely often

On a scale of 1 to 5, how trustworthy do you think you are to residents?

1 2 3 4 5

Not very trustworthy Extremely trustworthy

I routinely ask the resident to repeat or explain medical instruction back to me to ensure they understood.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

I explain the purpose, dosage, and possible side effects of any new medication.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

I feel that I involve the residents in decisions about their daily care and medication schedule.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

I feel highly confident in my own understanding of the resident's treatment plan and medication.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

Which of the following qualities do you exhibit when communicating with residents? (Check all that apply)

- Attentiveness
- Patience
- Open-mindedness
- Inquisitiveness

In the scenario that a patient does not understand what you are trying to communicate, what steps would you likely take next?

Your answer _____

Please explain briefly the ways in which you try to communicate information to patients (e.g. asking them to teach it back, writing abbreviated notes, repeating instructions, drawing simple pictures, demonstrating an action, etc.).

Your answer _____

[Back](#)

[Submit](#)

[Clear form](#)

Appendix D. Brief Health Literacy Screener and Morisky Medication Adherence Scale**Residents**

Please begin with the Brief Health Literacy Screener (BHLS) and Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-4). This is a 7-item questionnaire in total and should take you approximately 8 minutes to complete.

How confident are you filling out medical forms by yourself? *

- Extremely
- Quite a bit
- Somewhat
- A little bit
- Not at all

How often do you have someone help you read hospital materials? *

- All of the time
- Most of the time
- Some of the time
- A little of the time
- None of the time

How often do you have problems learning about your medical condition because of difficulty understanding written information? *

- All of the time
- Most of the time
- Some of the time
- A little of the time
- None of the time

Do you ever forget to take your medicine? *

- Yes
- No

Do you ever have problems remembering to take your medication? *

- Yes
- No

When you feel better, do you sometimes stop taking your medicine? *

Yes

No

Sometimes if you feel worse when you take your medicine, do you stop taking it? *

Yes

No

[Back](#)

[Next](#)

[Clear form](#)

My CNA routinely asks me to repeat or explain medical instruction to make sure I understand.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

My CNA explains the purpose, dosage, and possible side effects of any new medication.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

My CNA involves me in decisions about my daily care and medication schedule.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

I feel highly confident in my understanding of my treatment plan and medication.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

Which of the following qualities does your CNA exhibit when communicating with you?
(Check all that apply)

- Attentiveness
- Patience
- Open-mindedness
- Inquisitiveness

In the scenario that you do not understand what your CNA is trying to communicate, what steps do they often take next?

Your answer _____

Please explain briefly the ways in which your CNA tries to communicate information to you (e.g. asking you to teach it back, writing abbreviated notes, repeating instructions, drawing simple pictures, demonstrating an action, etc.).

Your answer _____

[Back](#)

[Submit](#)

[Clear form](#)